

1 “He responded to the questioner with more than what was asked for”. The
2 *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of al-Bukhārī (194/810-256/870) and the instruction on
3 knowledge in the formative period of Islam.
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6 **Abstract.**

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8 *‘ilm* (knowledge) is a key notion in the formative period of Islam, despite its neglected examination as
9 a sole concept and literary phenomenon. This article examines the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of al-Bukhārī (d.
10 256/870), located at the beginning of his *Ṣaḥīḥ*. Representing an innovative turn in the textual
11 trajectory of *‘ilm*, differences between the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* and preceding *‘ilm* narratives are apparent.
12 Similarly, echoes of the *Kitāb al-adab*, a unique paradigm of *ḥadīth* and *adab*, written by Ibn Abī
13 Shayba (d. 235/849) suggest that the early correlation between *ḥadīth* and *adab* helped to establish
14 *‘ilm* as a preface book in *muṣannaf* collections. In light of understanding this intertextual dynamic, I
15 cross-examine earlier *‘ilm* themes and those narrative elements inaugurated by al-Bukhārī. I conclude
16 that the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* represents a unique work of *‘ilm al-ḥadīth*: a technical study on teaching *‘ilm*.
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19 **Abbreviations:** *EAL* = *Encyclopedia of Arabic literature*. ed(s). Julie Scott Meisami and Paul Starkey,
20 (London: Routledge, 2010); *EI²* = *Encyclopedia of Islam*, Second Edition Online, ed(s). P. Bearman,
21 Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs (Leiden: Brill, 2012); *EI THREE* =
22 *Encyclopedia of Islam THREE* Online, ed(s). Kate Fleet, Gudrun Krämer, Denis Matringe, John
23 Nawas and Evertt Rowson (Leiden: Brill, 2015-2018); *EQ* = *Encyclopaedia of the Qur’ān* Online.
24 ed(s). Jane Dammen McAuliffe and William A. Graham (Leiden: Brill, 2001-2006); *al-Bukhārī, ‘ilm* =
25 Muḥammad b. Ismā‘īl al-Bukhārī, *Kitāb al-‘ilm* in *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī*, 5 vols. (Beirut, Damascus: al-
26 Maktabat al-‘Aṣriyya, 2000), vol. 1, pp. 45-69.
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28 **Keywords:** al-Bukhārī; *‘ilm*; *ḥadīth*; knowledge; Ibn Abī Shayba; *adab*;
29 education; Classical Arabic literature.
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Introduction.

In the formative period of Islam, *‘ilm* (knowledge) is the notion used to refer to the understanding of the transmission of the Qur’ānic revelation and *ḥadīth*, which, quoting Claude Gilliot, “takes place in a continuum”.¹ Paired with *‘amal* (practice), *‘ilm* will be the broad term, encompassing *āthār* (traces) and *akhbār* (reports).

This article examines the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of al-Bukhārī (d. 256/870),² the third book of the *Ṣaḥīḥ*, regarded as the first canonised *muṣannaf* (collection),³ alongside the other *Ṣaḥīḥ* of Muslim al-Ḥajjāj (d. 261/874). Situated at the beginning of the collection, the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* represents an innovative turn in the textual arrangement of *‘ilm* books in *muṣannafs* of the late second/eighth century under the *‘alā al-abwāb* (arranged by topics) structure.

Conceived as one of the earliest organised books on knowledge, there is a significant shortcoming of studies examining its correlation to previous *‘ilm* books. The latter and their study have been neglected by scholarship due to the textual and epistemological redundancy of *ḥadīth* as *‘ilm*, let alone the thematic analysis of *‘ilm* books, based on the themes and subplots which help to understand *‘ilm* as a literary phenomenon.⁴

Al-Bukhārī’s contribution to *‘ilm* was undoubtedly aided by the foundational work of al-Shāfi‘ī (d. 204/820) and the principles of *‘ilm khāṣṣa* (specialist knowledge) and *‘ilm al-‘amma* (common knowledge). Conceived as a middle ground position between the *aṣḥāb al-ra‘y* (companions of reason) and the *aṣḥāb al-ḥadīth* (companions of tradition), al-Shāfi‘ī introduced the discussion

1 Ed., “‘ilm”, in *EI*²; see ‘-l-m in *EQ*; Robson, James, “Ḥadīth”, in *EI*²; Pavlovitch, Pavel, “Ḥadīth”, in *EI THREE*. Boer, Tjitze J., Gardet, Louis, Berque, Jacques, and Ed., “‘Amal”, in *EI*²; Claude Gilliot (ed.) *Education and Learning in the Early Islamic World, Formation of the Classical Islamic World*, vol. 43 (Farnham, Surrey, England; Burlington, VT: Ashgate Variorum, 2012), Introduction, xiii, xlvi.

2 The main sources used for this article are: ‘Abd al-Razzāq al-Ṣan‘ānī, *al-Muṣannaf* (Beirut: al-Maktab al-Islāmī, 1970); Mālik b. Anas, *Muwaṭṭa‘*, ed. Fu‘ād ‘Abd al-Bāqī, 2 vols. (Beirut: Dār Iḥyā al-Turāth, 1985); Abū Khaythama, *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, ed. Muḥammad Nāṣir al-Dīn Albānī (Riyāḍ: Maktabat al-ma‘ārif li-l-nashr wa-l-tawzī‘, 2001); Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, *Jāmi‘ bayān al-‘ilm*, (al-Dammām: Dār Ibn al-Jawzī, 1994), *idem*, (Cairo: Idārat al-Ṭibā‘ah al-Munīriyya, [19--?]); ‘Abd Allāh b. ‘Abd al-Rahmān al-Dārimī, *Kitāb al-musnad al-Jāmi‘*, ed. Nabīl b. Hāshim b. ‘Abd Allāh al-Ghamrī (Dār al-Bashā‘ir al-Islāmiyya, 2013), ed. Ḥusayn Salīm Asad al-Dārānī (Dār al-Mughnī li-l-nashr wa-l-tawzī‘, 2000); Ibn Abī Shayba, *Muṣannaf*, ed. Usāma b. Ibrāhīm b. Muḥammad, 15 vols. (Cairo: al-Fārūq al-Ḥadītha li-l-Ṭabā‘a wa-l-Nashr, 2008); *idem*, *Kitāb al-adab*, ed. Muḥammad Riḍā al-Qahwājī, 2 vols. (Beirut: Dār al-Bashā‘ir al-Islāmiyya, 1999); Abū Bakr Aḥmad ibn ‘Alī Khaṭīb al-Baghdādī, *Tārikh Baghdād*, 14 vols (Cairo: Maktabat al-Khānjī, 1931), ed. Bashshār ‘Uwād, 16 vols. (Beirut: Dār Gharb al-Islāmī, 2002); Ibn Ḥajar al-‘Asqalānī, *Tahdhīb al-tahdhīb* (India: Dā‘irat-l-Ma‘ārif al-Nizāmiyya al-Hind, 1908).

3 Juynboll, Gautier H.A., “Muṣannaf”, “Tadwīn” in *EI*².

4 Raymond Trousson, *Les Études de Thèmes: Un Problème de Littérature Comparée; Essai de Méthodologie*, (Paris: Lettres Modernes, 1965); Elisabeth Frenzel, *Stoff-Und Motivgeschichte*, 2., Aufl, Grundlagen Der Germanistik 3 (Berlin: E. Schmidt, 1974); Claude Bremond, Joshua Landy and Thomas Pavel, *Thematics: New Approaches* (Albany: SUNY Press, 1995); Sebastian Luft and Soren Overgaard, ed(s)., *The Routledge Companion to Phenomenology* (London: Routledge, 2011). See also Stetter Eckart, *Topoi und Schemata im ḥadīth* (Diss., Tübingen), 1965.

1 on the legal framework of *farā'iq* (obligatory duties), distinguishing between *farḍ*
2 *ʿayn* (duty incumbent on every individual) and *farḍ kifāya* (incumbent on the
3 majority, but when enough Muslims perform it, others are discharged from doing
4 it).⁵ Conceived as *warathat al-anbiyā'* (Heirs of the Prophet), the *ʿulamā'*,⁶ will
5 confine the transmission of *ʿilm* to them exclusively, motivated by the principles
6 of *ʿilm khāṣṣa* and *farḍ kifāya*.

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9 Also, the emergence of the *Kitāb al-ʿilm* may be better understood through the
10 lens of the *Miḥna*, despite its “mythical status” in Western scholarship and its
11 recent challenged historicity.⁷ Echoes of the trial presumably helped to build a
12 collective practice of *ʿilm*, amongst the *ʿulamā'*, articulating the core principles
13 of *ṣunnī* scholarship.

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16 On the literary level, the *Kitāb al-ʿilm* is a work on *ḥadīth* but it bears
17 resemblance to early developments of *adab* (education, etiquette),⁸ where the
18 first attempts to explore the correlation between *ʿilm* and *adab* surfaced. One of
19 the earliest paradigms where *ḥadīth* and *adab* merged was the *Kitāb al-adab*, a
20 book within the *Muṣannaf* (The Collection) of Ibn Abī Shayba (d.235/849),
21 teacher of al-Bukhārī. This paired treatment would be signaled in another work
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28 5 Ignaz Goldziher, *The Zāhiris: Their doctrine and their history*, translated and edited by
29 Wolfgang Behn (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1971 [1884]), pp. 3-19; Joseph Schacht, *The Origins of*
30 *Muhammadan Jurisprudence* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1950), pp. 36, 56, 98; *idem.*, “Ahl al-
31 *Ḥadīth*”, and “Aṣḥāb al-Raʿy”, in *EI²*; Muḥammad b. Idrīs al-Shāfiʿī, *The Epistle on Legal Theory*,
32 Library of Arabic Literature (New York; London: New York University, 2013); Joseph E. Lowry,
33 *Early Islamic Legal Theory: The Risāla of Muḥammad Ibn Idrīs Al-Shāfiʿī*, Studies in Islamic Law
34 and Society; vol. 30 (Leiden; Boston: Brill, 2007); Aysha Musa, *Hadīth as Scripture: Discussions*
35 *on the Authority of Prophetic Traditions in Islam* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2008) p. 47; Christopher
36 Melchert, “Traditionist-Jurisprudents and the Framing of Islamic Law,” *Islamic Law and Society*
37 8, no. 3 (2001): 383-406, p. 383; Michael Bonner, “Jaʿāʾil and Holy War in Early Islam”, *Der*
38 *Islam*, 68 (1991): 45-64, p. 46. Another widely used term for duty in the legal literature is *wājib*;
39 see A. Kevin Reinhart, “Like the Difference Between Heaven and Earth: Ḥanafī and Shāfiʿī
40 Discussions of Farḍ and Wājib in Theology and Uṣūl”, *Studies in Islamic Legal Theory*, ed.
41 Bernard G. Weiss (Leiden: Brill, 2002), p. 216; Abdul Salām Shukrī, “The relationship between
42 *ʿilm* and *khbar*”, PhD Thesis, St Andrews University, 1999, p. 154.

43 6 Gilliot, Claude., Repp, Richard C., Nizami, Khaliq A., Hooker, Michael B., Lin, Chang-Kuan
44 and Hunwick, John O., “*ʿUlamā'*”, in *EI²*.

45 7 Scott C. Lucas, *Constructive Critics, Ḥadīth Literature, and the Articulation of Sunnī Islam: The*
46 *Legacy of the Generation of Ibn Saʿd, Ibn Maʿīn, and Ibn Ḥanbal*, Islamic History and
47 Civilization; vol. 51 (Leiden: Boston: Brill, 2004), p. 4, n.13, p.192; Christopher Melchert,
48 “Religious Policies of the Caliphs from Al-Mutawakkil to Al-Muqtadir, AH 232-295/A D 847-908,”
49 *Islamic Law and Society* 3, no. 3 (1996): 316–42, pp. 318-320, p. 325, p. 330; John P. Turner,
50 *Inquisition in Early Islam: The Competition for Political and Religious Authority in the Abbasid*
51 *Empire* (Bloomsbury Academic, 2013).

52 8 Gabrieli, Francesco, “Adab”, in *EI²*; Hilary Kilpatrick, “Adab,” in *EAL*, vol. 1, p. 56; Bo
53 Holmberg, “Adab and Arabic Literature” in *Literary History: Towards a Global Perspective*, ed.
54 by A. Pettersson [et al.] (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2006) pp. 181-205; S. A. Bonebakker, “Adab and
55 the Concept of Belles-Lettres,” in *The Cambridge History of Arabic Literature: Abbasid Belles-*
56 *Lettres*, ed. Julia Ashtiany (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990) pp. 180-205; Michael
57 Allan, “How Adab Became Literary: Formalism, Orientalism and the Institutions of World
58 Literature”, *Journal of Arabic Literature* 43, no. 2–3 (2012): 172-196, Hämeen-Anttila, Jaakko,
59 “Adab a) Arabic, early developments” in *EI THREE*; Enderwitz, Susanne, “Adab b) and Islamic
60 scholarship in the ʿAbbāsīd period”, in *EI THREE*.

1 of al-Bukhārī, the *Adab al-mufrad*. Overall, the study of the textual interaction of
2 both notions has been overlooked in scholarship.⁹

3 Even though the textual trajectory of *‘ilm* is one largely dominated by popular
4 but *ḍa‘īf* (weak) *ḥadīth*, and a presumably later assembly of collections, *‘ilm* as
5 a sole concept could, with these works, be said to have reached an
6 authoritative, textual development. Al-Bukhārī contributed to a new didactic
7 trend, similarly to his teacher Ibn Abī Shayba, providing a teacher’s handbook
8 as a method of *taḥammul al-‘ilm* (carrying knowledge of *ḥadīth*).¹⁰

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11 The first section provides a critical framework of *‘ilm* and its themes and the
12 correlation with early *adab* developments. Preceded by an overview of the life of
13 al-Bukhārī and the *Ṣaḥīḥ*, the second section presents the analysis of the *Kitāb*
14 *al-‘ilm*. In connection to preceding *‘ilm* narratives, the third section argues for
15 the examination of the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* as an original paradigm. The article ends
16 with a general insight into the contribution of al-Bukhārī to the textual trajectory
17 of *‘ilm*.
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21 On a methodological note,¹¹ this article will use the proper Arabic term *‘ilm*, as
22 the English translation does not encompass the full connotations of the notion.
23 To clarify terminology, I will refer to *‘ilm* narratives as the first evidence
24 of *‘ilm* as a theme under the formal structures of *kitābs* and *bābs*. The question
25 on the authenticity and provenance of *asānids* demands a further analysis and
26 is not the aim of this article. On early authorities and transmitters, I refer to the
27 contributions of Nabia Abbott, Muṣṭafá A‘zamī and Gautier Juynboll.¹²
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44 9 The *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of Ibn Qutayba (d. 276/889), is another original paradigm of an *‘ilm* book in a
45 proper *adab* encyclopaedia, the *‘Uyūn al-akḥbār*. Both texts are the main corpus of my
46 dissertation. “Narratives of Knowledge and Conduct Practices: *‘ilm* and *Adab* in Classical Arabic
47 literature (2/8-3/9 centuries)”, St Andrews University, *forthcoming*. My study provides a
48 perspective on the complex correlation between both notions and their textual interaction,
49 mapping different stages of *‘ilm* in *ḥadīth* literature and in early *adab* developments.

50 10 Muḥammad Muṣṭafá A‘zamī, *Studies in Early Ḥadīth Literature: With a Critical Edition of*
51 *Some Early Texts* (Kuala Lumpur: Islamic Book Trust, 2000), p. 183; *idem*, *Studies in Ḥadīth*
52 *Methodology and Literature* (Malaysia: Islamic Teaching Center, 1978), p. 16; A‘zamī, *Studies*.

53 11 All translations are mine except otherwise indicated. I include English plurals of Arabic terms
54 such as *kitāb* or *bāb*. Full citations will be followed by shortened citations for the same sources.
55 I use the English translation of the Qur’ān by Arthur. J. Arberry: *The Koran Interpreted: A*
56 *Translation* (New York: Macmillan, 1974).

57 12 Nabia Abbott, *Studies in Arabic Literary Papyri*, The University of Chicago Oriental Institute
58 Publications, 3 vols. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1957), vol. 2, p. 22; Gautier H. A.
59 Juynboll, *Muslim Tradition. Studies in Chronology, Provenance and Authorship of Early Ḥadīth*
60 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008), p. 39 onwards.
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1 1. *Ḥadīth* as *‘ilm*: a critical framework of knowledge in early formative Islam.
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3 Knowledge¹³ and religion¹⁴ are concepts that have an outstanding presence
4 within the context of premodern Arabic literature. Islam appeared amidst Jewish
5 and Christian trends in their common prophetic, scriptural and exegetical
6 phases. The practice of creed triggered a transmission and creation of
7 knowledge in group commitment. These are central traits in Late Antiquity as a
8 formative period of monotheistic Abrahamic religiosities, which, regarded by
9 Guy Stroumsa as a “*preparatio coranica*”,¹⁵ paved the way for the emergence of
10 Islam.
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14 *‘Ilm* is an insight from God,¹⁶ that protects the *‘ulamā*’ upon *yawm al-qiyāma*
15 (Day of Resurrection), as shown in Q 16:27, Q 17:107 or Q 19:43. It is not
16 coincidental that this will be one of the most significant themes in *‘ilm*
17 narratives. Those with *‘ilm* are said to fear God (Q 35:28). They perceive and
18 comprehend, and will be elevated by God, unlike “ignorants”.¹⁷
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22 On the level of epistemology, *‘ilm* can be conceived as a justified, true belief,
23 and also as a practice that develops in accordance with an experience and an
24 awareness of a surrounding reality.¹⁸ Practice takes us to an important principle
25 associated with *‘ilm*: *‘amal*. In addition to their phonetic symmetry, *‘ilm* and
26 *‘amal* started operating together at the first stages of the Qur’ānic revelation.
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30 13 Duncan Pritchard, *What Is This Thing Called Knowledge?* (London; New York: Routledge,
31 2006); Paul K. Moser, ed., *The Oxford Handbook of Epistemology* (New York: Oxford University
32 Press, 2005); Markus Asper et al., “Representing Authority in Ancient Knowledge Texts” in
33 *Space and Knowledge*, Special Volume 6 (December 15, 2016): 389-417, p. 392, p. 396.

34 14 Feil, Ernst, Antes, Peter, Schwöbel, Christoph, Herms, Eilert, Küster, Volker and Schmidt-
35 Rost, Reinhard, “Religion”, in *Religion Past and Present Online*; Emile Durkheim, *The*
36 *elementary forms of religious Life*, ed. Mark Sydney Cladis, trans. Carol Cosman, (Oxford:
37 Oxford University Press, 2008); Max Weber, *The Sociology of Religion* (London: Methuen,
38 1965), p. 1.

39 15 Patricia Crone and Michael A. Cook, *Hagarism: The Making of the Islamic World*
40 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1977), vii; Garth Fowden, *Before and After*
41 *Muhammad: The First Millennium Refocused*, (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2013), pp.
42 55-57; Peter Brown, *The Making of Late Antiquity*, (Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University
43 Press, 1978), p. 8; ‘Azīz ‘Aẓma, *The Emergence of Islam in Late Antiquity: Allāh and His People*
44 (New York; Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014), pp. 14-15, Stroumsa, Guy G.
45 “Envoi: Athens, Jerusalem, Mecca: praeparatio coranica” in *The Making of the Abrahamic*
46 *Religions in Late Antiquity* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015), *Oxford Scholarship Online*.

47 16 It is not the aim of this article to present the textual evidence of *‘ilm* in pre-Islamic poetry and
48 the Qur’ān. Similarly, there are other notions in the Qur’ān, such as *ma’rifā* (understanding) *fiqh*
49 (judgement, law), *shu’r* (poetry) that refer to the truth, perception and comprehension of
50 Creation. They are equivalences to knowledge which appear in connection to *‘ilm* but their
51 examination demands further analysis. For the semantic derivations of the term *‘ilm* in early
52 Arabic Poetry and in the Qur’ān, see digital resources of the following projects: *Arabic*
53 *Semantics in Transition*, and *Corpus Coranicum*. See: Rippin, Andrew, “Tafsīr”, in *EL²*; *idem*,
54 *Approaches to the History of the Interpretation of the Qur’ān* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1988).

55 17 The opposite of knowledge is *jahl* (ignorance); also expressed as not having *hudā*
56 (guidance), see Shepard, William E., “Ignorance”, in *EQ*; Walker, Paul E., “Knowledge and
57 Learning”, in *EQ*.

58 18 Edmund Gettier, “Is Justified True Belief Knowledge?” in *Analysis*, vol. 23, 6, (June 1963),
59 pp. 121-123; Pritchard, *Knowledge*, p. 6; John Hyman, *Action, Knowledge, and Will* (Oxford
60 University Press, 2017), p. 190.
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1 The Qur'ān can be understood as a creative episode in Late Antiquity; upon its
2 reception, Muslims attributed value to it. This represents the “double aspect of
3 the creative action”, claimed by Marshall Hodgson.¹⁹

4 In the formative period of Islam, *‘ilm* will be the main method and skill to
5 understand *ḥadīth*,²⁰ which is the authoritative principle of *‘ilm*. Due to this
6 complex, epistemological redundancy, there has been a significant shortcoming
7 of studies on *‘ilm* as a sole concept. It can be argued that scholarship on *ḥadīth*
8 criticism²¹ understandably overshadowed the full extension of *‘ilm*. Rosenthal's
9 monograph is the only work fully dedicated to *‘ilm*, alerting about the
10 problematics of its translation and examination in the introduction of his
11 foundational contribution.²²

12 Framed under the early conquests, the aftermath of the First and Second Fitna
13 civil wars, the first attempt to collect *‘ilm* as the Tradition of the Prophet (*sunnat*
14 *al-nabī*) took place under the reign of ‘Abd al-Malik (r. 65/685-86/705). During
15 the caliphate of ‘Umar II (r. 99/717-101/720), the request to record *‘ilm* was
16 made to ‘Amr b. Ḥazm (d. ca. 120/738) and to al-Zuhrī (d. 124/741).²³ The
17 foundational network of the *qurrā* (reciters),²⁴ and the *quṣṣāṣ* (story-tellers),²⁵
18 as early transmitters of *‘ilm* and Qur'ānic exegesis surfaced in first/seventh
19 century ‘Irāq, but were gradually displaced by Traditionists and the *‘ulamā*.

20 Understood as a religious imperative, *‘ilm* and its collection promoted an
21 intellectual quest and became a crucial factor in the development of authority
22 and textual tradition. *Ṭalab al-‘ilm* (pursuit of knowledge) is the most
23 representative collocation in the dimension of *‘ilm* writings, even though its
24 associated traditions are distinguished by their *ḍa‘īf* nature, making it a highly
25 spurious framework.²⁶ It has been challenged as a widespread practice,
26 construed probably more as a religious imaginaire.²⁷ However, the collocation
27 contributed to the identity of the *‘ulamā*, who became a dynamic, global
28 scriptural community in contact also by means of *ḥajj* (pilgrimage) networks.

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39 19 Marshall G. S. Hodgson, *The Venture of Islam, Volume 1: The Classical Age of Islam*
40 (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1977), vol. 1, p. 81, p. 88, n. 6, p. 362.

41 20 Juynboll, *Muslim Tradition*, p. 33.

42 21 Herbert Berg, *The Development of Exegesis in Early Islam: The Authenticity of Muslim*
43 *Literature from the Formative Period* (London: Routledge, 2009); Gautier H. A. Juynboll, ed.,
44 *Studies on the First Century of Islamic Society* (Carbondale: Southern Illinois University Press,
45 1982); Nadia Abbott, “Ḥadīth Literature-II: Collection and Transmission of Ḥadīth” in *Arabic*
46 *Literature to the End of the Umayyad Period*, Cambridge History of Arabic Literature, chapter
47 11, pp. 289-298; Mustafa Shah, *The Ḥadīth, Critical Concepts in Islamic Studies* (New York:
48 Routledge, 2010).

49 22 Franz Rosenthal, *Knowledge Triumphant; the Concept of Knowledge in Medieval Islam*.
50 (Leiden: Brill, 1970), p. 1, p. 3.

51 23 Juynboll, *Muslim Tradition*, p. 19, p. 34, p. 41; Abbott, II, p. 22, p. 53.

52 24 Nagel, Tilman, “Ḳurrā”, in *EL*; Gautier H. A. Juynboll, “The Qurra’ in early Islamic history”,
53 *JESHO*, xvi (1973), pp. 113-129; Mustafa Shah, “The Quest for the Origins of the Qurra’ in the
54 Classical Islamic Tradition”, *Journal of Qur’anic Studies* 7, no. 2 (2005): pp. 1-35.

55 25 Lyall R. Armstrong, *The Quṣṣāṣ of Early Islam* (Leiden, Brill, 2016), see section on *‘ilm*,
56 chapter 3, p. 155, onwards; Johannes Pedersen, “The Islamic preacher wā’iz, mudhakkir, qāṣṣ”
57 in Claude Gilliot, (ed), *Education*, 93-112; Charles Pellat, “Ḳāṣṣ”, in *EL*.

58 26 Rosenthal, *Knowledge*, p. 89; Juynboll, *Muslim Tradition*, pp. 66-70.

59 27 Gilliot, *Education, Introduction*, xlix; W. Montgomery Watt, *The Formative Period of Islamic*
60 *Thought* (Oxford: Oneworld Publications, 1998), p. 64.

1 This is highly visible in the case of the 'ulamā' of al-Andalus, and the
2 introduction of 'ilm al-ḥadīth.²⁸ Ṭalab al-'ilm would also be associated to the
3 genre of riḥla (traveling), where riḥla fī ṭalab al-'ilm, traveling in pursuit of
4 collecting traditions, would become a parallel, literary outcome of this
5 phenomenon.²⁹
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7 Evidenced in the scholarship of the 'ulama', 'ilm becomes an epistemological
8 notion, a particular "knowledge", in its own textual manifestations, gradually
9 developing into a discursive practice and a literary creation. As a discourse,³⁰
10 'ilm exemplifies a practice of knowledge formation across a reality of religious
11 beliefs, norms and values performed by society. As a literary creation, 'ilm
12 incorporates thematic subjects which showcase the way oral knowledge was
13 interpreted and received, which promoted a process of transmission, reshaping
14 and further creation of knowledge. Quoting Tarif Khalidi:³¹
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16

17 In passing on the wisdom of ancestors these scholars believed that they were transmitters
18 rather than creators. But the process of transmission became, as so often in the history of
19 cultures, creation through transmission.
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26 1.1. The textual development of "knowledge" as a narrative in ḥadīth literature.

27
28 At the early stages of Arabic historical writing, the development of 'ilm
29 narratives exemplifies the double process of both oral and written modes of
30 knowledge transmission.³² Riwāya (oral transmission) was the primitive form of
31 'ilm that was endorsed by the notion of tadwīn (collecting, fixing down).³³ This
32 produced a modular division of knowledge evidenced by the 'alā-l-abwāb
33 arrangement in muṣannafs.
34

35 In addition, the written fixation of 'ilm as ḥadīth is one of the earliest
36 epistemological debates in Arabic literature. In fact, it can be argued that the
37 appearance of sections on 'ilm were motivated by the epistemic debate on
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41 28 Maribel Fierro, "The Introduction of Ḥadīth in Al-Andalus (2nd/8th-3rd/9th Centuries)," *Der*
42 *Islam* 66, no. 1 (2009): pp. 68–93, p. 77; *idem*, "The Control of Knowledge in Islamic Societies,"
43 *Al-Qantara: Revista de Estudios Árabes* 35, no. 1 (2014): pp. 127-34; Rosenthal, Franz,
44 "Awā'il", in *EI*²; Bernards, Monique, "Awā'il", in *EI THREE*.

45 29 Ian R. Netton, "Riḥla", in *EI*²; Gellens, Sam I. "The Search for Knowledge in Medieval Muslim
46 Societies: A Comparative Approach" in *Muslim Travellers: Pilgrimage, Migration, and the*
47 *Religious Imagination. Comparative Studies on Muslim Societies*, Dale F. Eickelman and James
48 Piscatori, ed(s). (California: University of California Press, 1990), p. 50, p. 53.

49 30 Michel Foucault, *The Archaeology of Knowledge*, trans. Alan Sheridan, (London, England)
50 (New York: Pantheon Books, 1972), pp. 182-183.

51 31 Tarif Khalidi, *Arabic Historical Thought in the Classical Period*, Cambridge Studies in Islamic
52 Civilization (Cambridge; New York: Cambridge University Press, 1994), p. 18; Norman Calder,
53 *Studies in Early Muslim Jurisprudence* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1993), p. 162.

54 32 Gregor Schoeler, *The Genesis of Literature in Islam: From the Aural to the Read*, trans.
55 Shawkat M. Toorawa. The New Edinburgh Islamic Surveys (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University
56 Press, 2009), p. 21, p. 37; *idem*: "Writing and Publishing on the Use and Function of Writing in
57 the First Centuries of Islam," *Arabica* 44, no. 3 (January 1, 1997): pp. 423-35.

58 33 Leder, Stefan, "Riwāya", in *EI*²; *idem*, "Understanding a Text Through Its Transmission", in
59 *Manuscript Notes as Documentary Sources*, Andreas Görke and Konrad Hirschler, eds.
60 (Würzburg: Ergon Verlag, 2012); Juynboll, "Tadwīn" in *EI*².
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1 writing (or not) Tradition. This circumstance is reflected in the titles of the first
2 books on *‘ilm*, literally, termed *kitāb al-‘ilm* or *kitābat al-‘ilm*.

3
4 Early narratives of *‘ilm* surfaced between the late Umayyad and early ‘Abbāsīd
5 period, slightly before the formation of the canonical corpora of the *kutub al-*
6 *sitta*.³⁴ This is important to allocate the emergence of *‘ilm* writings in line with
7 Islamic historiography proper. In addition, second/eight century *taṣnīf* collections
8 have not survived in their original form, leaving only recensions, none dating
9 earlier than the third/ninth century.³⁵

10
11 The earliest “extant” *muṣannaf* works did not include sections on *‘ilm*, but
12 incorporated traditions on *‘ilm* that would later appear in prospective *‘ilm* books,
13 such as the *Sīra* (Biography of the Prophet) by Ibn Ishāq (d. 151/768),³⁶; the
14 *Kitāb al-kharāj* (Book on Taxation) and the *Kitāb al-āthār* (Book of Traditions) of
15 Abū Yūsuf Ya‘qūb b. Ibrāhīm (d. 182/798); the *Kitāb al-āthār* (Book of traditions)
16 of Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan al-Shaybānī (d. 189/805); and the *Muṣannaf* of ‘Abd
17 al-Razzāq b. Hammām al-Ṣan‘ānī (d. 211/827).³⁷

18
19 Al-Ṣan‘ānī transmitted the *Jāmi‘* of Ma‘mar b. Rāshid (d. 153/770), included in
20 most editions of the *Muṣannaf*. The *Jāmi‘* has a *bāb al-‘ilm* and a *bāb kitāb al-*
21 *‘ilm*. It precedes the *Kitāb Mā ja‘ā fī ṭalab al-‘ilm* (On the pursuit of *‘ilm*) in the
22 *Muwāṭṭa‘* of Mālik b. Anas (d.179/795), which has only one report featuring
23 Luqmān al-Ḥakīm advising his son. The presumable later amalgamation and
24 attribution of both sections on *‘ilm* have been subject to debate.³⁸

25
26 One of the earliest books on *‘ilm* is the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of Ibn Wahb (d. 197/813),
27 included in his *Jāmi‘*,³⁹ – only a fragment of which has been edited – and cited
28 by Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr in the *Jāmi‘ bayān al-‘ilm* and in the *Kitāb al-majālis*, with
29 more than 160 quotations. The *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of Abū Khaythama (d. 234/849) is
30 another important *‘ilm* book,⁴⁰ which is not a *muṣannaf* proper and does not
31 follow the *‘alā-al-abwāb* structure, and where Abū Khaythama is the main
32 transmitter. The contributions of al-Shāfi‘ī (d. 204/820) are jurisprudential treatises
33 on *ḥadīth*, not distinguished by literary elements and themes, unlike the
34 aforementioned works.

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34 Namely, the *Ṣaḥīḥ* of al-Bukhārī (d. 256/870) and Muslim (d. 261/875); the *Sunan* of Abū Dāwūd (d. 275/889); the *Jāmi‘* (also *Sunan*) of al-Tirmidhī (d. 279/892); *Sunan* of al-Nasā‘ī (d. 303/915) also known as *Sunan al-Ṣuḡhrā*; and *Sunan* of Ibn Māja (d. 273/886). Some authorities include *al-Muwāṭṭa‘* by Mālik b. Anas (d.179/795) as the sixth collection.

35 It should be noted that the assembly of *muṣannafs* puts the arrangement of *‘ilm* narratives on the radar. Also, additional books on *‘ilm* are most likely, subject to appear, as one can hardly exclude the possibility of finding a new manuscript with a totally different order of the topics. This is also due to editorial practices in *ḥadīth* collections, which add headings and titles in relation to *‘ilm* drawing on the *‘alā l-abwāb* structure.

36 Ibn Hishām, *al-Sīra al-nabawiyya*, ed. Suhayl Zakār (Beirut: Dār al-Fikr, 1978); Abū Yūsuf Ya‘qūb, *Kitāb al-kharāj* (Beirut: Dār al-Ma‘rifa, 1979) and *Kitāb al-āthār*, ed. al-Afghānī Abū-l-Wafā (Beirut: Dār Kutub al-‘Ilmiyya, n.d.); Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan al-Shaybānī, *Kitāb al-āthār*, 2 vols. (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-‘Ilmiyya, 1993; ‘Abd al-Razzāq al-Ṣan‘ānī, *al-Muṣannaf*, (Beirut: al-Maktab al-Islāmī, 1970).

37 Motzki, Harald, “al-Ṣan‘ānī”, in *EI²*, *EI THREE*.

38 Mālik, *Muwāṭṭa‘*, vol. 2, p. 1002, report 1. Rosenthal, *Knowledge*, p. 70.

39 David-Weill, Jean, “Ibn Wahb”, in *EI²*.

40 Pellat, Charles, “Ibn Abī Khaythama” in *EI²*.

1 The most important recurrent themes are the effacement of *‘ilm* and scholars
2 upon *yawm al-qiyāma*. Knowledge will be lost through the disappearance of
3 scholars, so *‘ilm* and the scholar form an inextricable bond. An early *ḥadīth* on
4 this motif can be found in the *bāb al-‘ilm* of Ma‘mar b. Rāshid, narrated by Ibn
5 Mas‘ūd (d. 32/652–653):⁴¹

6
7
8 Ibn Mas‘ūd: Scholars, you have an obligation towards knowledge (*‘ilm*) before it is lifted away;
9 its effacement is doom for its people. And even if some of you don't know when you will need it,
10 or what you will need from it, you have an obligation towards *‘ilm*.

11
12 The momentum is best conveyed in one of the most recurrent, Prophetical
13 reports in *‘ilm* narratives:⁴²

14
15 Whoever conceals knowledge, God will bridle him with reins of fire on the Day of Resurrection.

16 *Ṭalab al-‘ilm* is one of the most representative collocations and themes of *‘ilm*,
17 as shown in what is probably the most popular prophetical report: “*Ṭalab al-‘ilm*
18 *farīḍa ‘alā kull Muslim*” (Seeking knowledge is an obligation for every Muslim).⁴³
19 Ziyād b. Maymūn (fl. first half of the second/eighth century) is said to have
20 invented the report. The *Sunan* of Ibn Māja (d. 273/886) is the only one of the
21 *kuttub al-sitta* to include it.⁴⁴ It has a second variant, forged by the alleged
22 *kadhhdhāb* (liar, untrustworthy) Ṭarīf b. Sulaymān Abū l-‘Ātika. (fl. 160/177). It is
23 one of the most widespread reports on *‘ilm* narratives:
24
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26
27
28 Search for knowledge even as far as China, as searching for knowledge is an obligation for
29 every Muslim.

30
31 Regarding this last report, Juynboll claims that the second part was forged by
32 Ḥafṣ b. Sulaymān (d. 180/796), an important *kadhhdhāb*.

33
34
35 *‘ilm* narratives are defined by the textual characterisation of the *‘ulamā’* who at
36 this period were not a consolidated institution. Their justification – mostly
37 through Prophetical *ḥadīth* – is strongly correlated to their legitimacy as an
38 emerging class in society based on *riyāsa* (leadership) after Muḥammad ⁴⁵ and
39 early Islam as a pietistic movement:⁴⁶

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42 Ibn ‘Abbās: Indeed, every creature, even a fish in the sea, asks for forgiveness for whomsoever
43 teaches good to people.

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50 41 ‘Abd al-Razzāq, *al-Muṣannaf*, vol. 11, p. 252, report 20465; A‘zamī, *Studies*, p. 44.

51 42 Abū Khaythama, *Kitāb al-‘Ilm*, p. 26, report 53; Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, *Jāmi’*, vol. 1, 9, report 7; Ibn
52 ‘Abd al-Barr, *Jāmi’*, vol. 2, p. 839, report 1574.

53 43 Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, *Jāmi’*, vol. 1, p. 26, report 18, onwards; *idem*, (ed. Cairo), vol. 1, p. 7;
54 Juynboll, *Muslim Tradition*, pp. 68-9. Both sources provide additional references of the report in
55 other collections.

56 44 Ibn Māja, Muḥammad b. Yazīd, *Sunan Ibn Māja*, ed. Fu‘ād ‘Abd al-Bāqī, 2 vols. (Cairo: Dār
57 lḥyā’ al-Kutub al-‘Arabiya) vol. 1, 81, report 224.

58 45 Roy P. Mottahedeh, *Loyalty and Leadership in an Early Islamic Society*, Revol. ed. (London;
59 New York, St Martin’s Press, 2001), p. 135; Hodgson, *The Venture*, vol. 1, p. 255.

60 46 Fred McGraw Donner, *Narratives of Islamic Origins: The Beginnings of Islamic Historical*
61 *Writing* (Darwin Press, 1998), p. 114; Abū Khaythama, *Kitāb al-‘Ilm*, p. 9, report 6.

1 As a symmetrical argument to the image of piety, scholars who perform with
2 rogue intentions or show arrogance are shunned, reflecting that scholars and
3 their practice are subject to scrutiny. The paired treatment of *‘ilm* and *‘amal* is
4 indicative of how developing *‘ilm* narratives will promote that transmission of
5 *‘ilm* must come in compliance with action, manifesting the textual usage of their
6 phonetic symmetry:⁴⁷

7 ‘Abd Allāh: Oh, people, learn! Whoever has learned must act.
8
9

10 This textual environment shows at times a ranking between both notions. Early
11 traditionists could have been concerned with the fact that a performative excess
12 in *‘amal* could diminish the authoritative principle of *‘ilm* as expert knowledge,
13 and possibly even trigger non-orthodox views on *sunna*.
14

15
16 The acquisition of wealth amongst scholars triggers a moral debate in the
17 practice of *‘ilm*, but in early *muṣannaf* the relationship between accumulated
18 wealth and knowledge is not prominent. This controversy would be more
19 apparent in *adab*.
20

21
22 In the interconnection of action and creed, another subplot emerges in *‘ilm*
23 narratives. “*Lā adri*” (“I don’t know”) is a semantic tool to acknowledge the
24 understanding (or not) of *‘ilm* or a particular tradition. The use of this collocation
25 goes further beyond: it becomes an epistemic inquiry in relation to *‘ilm*. How
26 does a scholar know that *‘ilm* has been attained? This theme will be highly
27 prominent in the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of Ibn Qutayba,⁴⁸ showing an epistemological
28 similarity to the pre-Socratic paradox.⁴⁹
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33 1.2. The early correlation between *ḥadīth* and *adab*. 34

35 In this early period, *‘ilm* manifests itself in *ḥadīth* literature, but upon the
36 emergence of *adab* prose, it saw it itself appearing in two parallel literary
37 frameworks. Approaches to the correlation between *‘ilm-ḥadīth* and *adab* are
38 significantly scarce, in comparison to the widespread scholarship on *adab*.⁵⁰
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42 Early *adab* writers were amongst the first to explain the connotations between
43 *‘ilm-ḥadīth* and *adab* by discussing their relationship. The notion of *‘ilm* in the
44 *Risāla* (The Epistle) of ‘Abd al-Ḥamīd al-Kātib (d. 132/750) is conceived as a
45 *ṣinā‘a* (craft), a skill in the competitive performance of the *kuttāb* (secretaries).⁵¹
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48 47 Abū Khaythama, *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, p. 9, report 4.

49 48 Muḥammad ‘Abd al-Qādir Hātīm, *Uyūn al-akḥbār*, 4 vols. (Cairo: al-Mu‘assasat al-Miṣriyya
50 al-‘Āmma li-l-Ta’līf wa-l-Tarjama wa-l-Nashr, 1924-1930. Reprinted 1963).

51 49 The question remains whether this motif could also be connected to the apophatic or
52 negative theology. See Douglas B. Farrow, “Apophatic Theology,” *Religion Past and Present*,
53 April 1, 2011.

54 50 Rosenthal, *Knowledge*, p. 240, p. 251. Tarif Khalidi has also approached the correlation
55 between *‘ilm* and *adab*, see *Arabic Historical Thought*, Chapter Three, *History and Adab*, p. 83
56 onwards. For more recent approximations, see entries on *adab* by Hāmeen-Anttila and
57 Enderwitz in *EI THREE*.

58 51 al-Qalqashandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a‘shā*, 14 vols. (Cairo: Dār Kutub al-Miṣriyya, 1922), vol. 1, p. 85;
59 Muḥammad Kurd ‘Alī, *Rasā’il al-bulaghā’* (Miṣr: Dār al-Kutub al-‘Arabīya al-Kubrā, 1913), pp.
60 172-175; Wadād al-Qāḍī, “The Religious Foundation of Late Umayyad Ideology and Practice,”
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1 Collective memory, ancient lore and an archetypal vision of *‘ilm* are three
2 important traits in the *Adab al-kabīr* (The great education) of Ibn al-Muqaffa’ (ca.
3 102/720-139/756), who offered one of the earliest depictions of *‘ilm* paired with
4 *adab*.⁵²

5 Oh, pursuer of *adab*, if you seek the nature of *‘ilm*, first know the *uṣūl* (roots) and the *fuṣūl*
6 (branches).

7
8 Al-Jāhīz (d. 255/868-9) also attempted to define both notions in the *Risālat al-*
9 *mu‘allimīn*, a treatise aimed at teachers:⁵³

10 The term *mu‘allim* derives from *‘ilm*, whereas the *mu‘addib* (one who is instructed in *adab*) from
11 *adab*. We know that *‘ilm* is the root and *adab* is the branch; and *adab*, in addition, is divided into
12 *khulq* (moral character) and *riwāya* (transmission).

13
14 The *Kitāb al-adab* of Ibn Abī Shayba,⁵⁴ a book within his *Muṣannaf*,⁵⁵ merged
15 the structure of a *muṣannaf* with the *adab* framework. Born in Kūfa, Ibn Abī
16 Shayba was a prominent *ḥadīth* expert and *thiqa* (trustworthy), though many of
17 his reports do not refer to or include the Prophet, which is why he was labeled
18 as a *ḍa‘īf* transmitter.

19
20 Ibn Abī Shayba had an important role when the *Miḥna* was reversed by al-
21 Mutawakkil, who summoned Ibn Abī Shayba and his brother Uthmān (d.
22 239/853) to promote anti-Mu‘tazilī reports to refute the Jahmiyya (even though
23 they were accused of inventing reports).⁵⁶ The *Muṣannaf* appears connected to
24 several developments: the rise of *sunni ḥadīth* literature and *ḥadīth*-transmitter
25 criticism as a reaction to the Mu‘tazilite movement, the increasing power of the
26 *‘ulamā’* and, most importantly, the rise of Islam as a world creed.

27
28 The *Kitāb al-adab*⁵⁷ showcases the relationship between *ḥadīth* and *adab*. A
29 wide variety of chapters on social norms, etiquette in gatherings, purification
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34 in *Saber Religioso y Poder Político En El Islam. Actas Del Simposio Internacional (Granada, 15-*
35 *18 Octubre 1991)*, AECID, 1994, pp. 231-73; *idem*, “‘Abd al-Ḥamīd b. Yaḥyā al-Kātib” in *EL*
36 *THREE*.

37 52 Ibn al-Muqaffa’, *Āthār Ibn al-Muqaffa’* (Beirut: al-Kutub al-‘Ilmiyya, 1989), Jean Tardy,
38 “Traduction “d’al-Adab al-kabīr” d’Ibn al-Muqaffa’” in *Annales Islamologiques*, 27 (1993), pp.
39 181-223, p. 183.

40 53 al-Jāhīz, *Rasā’il al-Jāhīz*, ed. Muḥammad ‘Abd al-Salām Hārūn, 4 vols. (Beirut: Dār al-Jīl,
41 1991), vol. 3, p. 34.

42 54 al-Khaṭīb al-Baghdādī, *Tārīkh Baghdād*, vol. 11, pp. 259-267, n. 5138; al-Dhahabī, *Siyar*
43 *a’lām al-nubalā’*, ed. Shu‘ayb al-Arna‘ūt, et. al. (Beirut: Mu‘assasat al-Risāla, 1985), vol. 11,
44 pp. 122-127, n. 44; Ibn Ḥajar al-‘Asqalānī, *Tahdhīb*, vol. 6, pp. 2-4; Ibn al-Nadīm, *The Fihrist of*
45 *al-Nadīm* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1970), p. 553, section 6; Charles Pellat, ‘Ibn
46 Abī Shayba’ in *EL*²; Lawrence Conrad, “Ibn Abī Shayba,” in *EAL*, vol. 1, 306; Rosenthal,
47 *Knowledge*, p. 74, pp. 253-254.

48 55 The *Muṣannaf* draws on the narrations of relevant ‘Irāqī religious authorities from 2nd/8th
49 century. Ibn Abī Shayba’s reports are found in all of the *kutub al-sitta*. See Scott C. Lucas,
50 “Where Are the Legal Ḥadīth? A Study of the “Muṣannaf” of Ibn Abī Shayba,” *Islamic Law and*
51 *Society*, 15, n. 3, (2008): 283-314.

52 56 Lucas, “Where Are the Legal Ḥadīth?”, p. 285; Christopher Melchert, “Religious Policies”, pp.
53 322-323; *idem*, “Traditionist-Jurisprudents”, p. 388; John Burton, *An Introduction to the Hadīth*,
54 Islamic Surveys Series (Edinburgh: Edinburgh U. P., 1994), p. 120.

55 57 al-Qahwājī’s critical edition of the *Kitāb al-adab* is based on Ms. Damascus Maktabat al-
56 Zāhiriyya (↔183- 137/7/78). He claims that it could have been extracted from a previous
57 collection of reports dedicated to *akhlāq* (morals, ethics) and *adab nabawī* (teachings based on
58 Prophetical reports). The recension and presumably later arrangement of the book must be
59 taken into account. He points out to al-Bukhārī as the most possible candidate; see al-Qahwājī,
60 *Kitāb al-adab*, Introduction, vol. 1, p.11, p. 13, 69-70.
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1 rituals and methods of speech as conduct praxis emerge from this correlation. It
2 is an original pedagogical narrative with highly technical chapters on subjects
3 which had not surfaced in previous *muṣannafs*. Even though the book *Kitāb al-*
4 *adab* can be described neither as a book on *ḥadīth* nor *adab* exclusively, the
5 chapters seem to be broader under an *adab* framework, representing a new
6 literary trend and allowing a wider potential for exegetical education.

7 Al-Bukhārī, as a student of Abī Shayba, emerged with a similar innovative
8 attitude to his teacher. In the aftermath of the post-*Miḥna* events, in view of
9 providing a consistent systematization of *ḥadīth*, Al-Bukhārī made a decisive
10 arrangement: he initiated a *muṣannaf* with a proper book for understanding the
11 Prophetic tradition – a book on *‘ilm*.
12
13

14 2. Al-Bukhārī (d. 256/870) and the *Ṣaḥīḥ*.

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19 Abū ‘Abd Allāh Muḥammad b. Ismā‘īl b. al-Mughīra al-Bukhārī was born in
20 194/810 in the province of al-Bukhārā, current Uzbekistan. Most biographies⁵⁸
21 give account of his exceptional memory from a very young age and his early
22 devotion to *ḥadīth*. Al-Bukhārī travelled widely and collected a vast amount of
23 traditions. While in Naysābūr, he was accused of non-orthodox views and left
24 for Bukhārā. After some teaching discrepancies with the children of the *wālī* of
25 Bukhārā, he left for Khartank where he died in 256/870.
26
27

28
29 He is the noteworthy author of the *Ṣaḥīḥ*, which draws on the transmission of
30 the previous generation of early authorities, amalgamating the gamut of
31 600,000 reports in more than sixteen years. One of the most important
32 commentaries on the *Ṣaḥīḥ* is the *Fatḥ al-Bārī* (Victory of the Creator) of Ibn
33 Ḥajar al-‘Asqalānī (d. 852/1449).⁵⁹
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36 2.1. The *Kitāb al-‘ilm*: knowledge as an introductory chapter in *muṣannafs*.

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58 J. Robson, “al-Bukhārī, Muḥammad b. Ismā‘īl” in *EI*². The contributions of Jonathan Brown and Silvia Akar include the most relevant studies and prosopographical material on al-Bukhārī. See Jonathan Brown, *The Canonization of Al-Bukhārī and Muslim: The Formation and Function of the Sunnī Ḥadīth Canon*, Islamic History and Civilization; vol. 69 (Leiden; Boston: Brill, 2007), p. 47, p. 64, p. 362; Sylvia Akar, *But If You Desire God and His Messenger: The Concept of Choice in Ṣaḥīḥ Al-Bukhārī*, *Studia Orientalia*; 102 (Helsinki: Finnish Oriental Society, 2006), pp. 5-20; Ghassan Abdul-Jabbar, *Bukhari, Makers of Islamic Civilization* (London, New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2007).

59 Lucas, *Constructive Critics*, p. 21; I. Goldziher, *Muslim Studies* (London: Allen & Unwin, 1967), vol. 2, pp. 234-245.

60 The *Ṣaḥīḥ* and the section of knowledge enjoys wide scholarship inasmuch as translations, and commentaries. However, scholarship or an edition solely on the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* is hard to find. Rosenthal provided a translation of some chapters. See Rosenthal, *Knowledge*, p. 78.

1 Al-Bukhārī was not the first to include a section on *‘ilm* at the beginning of a
2 *muṣannaf*. The *Musnad* al-Dārimī (d. 235/865) includes several chapters on *‘ilm*
3 situated at the beginning of the collection. In al-Ghamrī’s edition,⁶¹ these
4 chapters are arranged under a *kitāb*, which is most likely an editorial addition.
5

6 The *Kitāb al-‘ilm* has 53 chapters. The reports are mostly prophetic, however
7 the *matn* (content) and accounts in the *bābs* have little connection to the titles.
8 The most significant themes in relation to *‘ilm* are found in the *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, but
9 while the disparity between content and titles might raise some doubts, it shows
10 that there was a need for precision and sophistication in the instruction of *‘ilm*.
11

12 Two chapters showcase the theme of *yawm al-qiyāma* and the disappearance
13 of scholars. Chapter 21 *Raf‘ al-‘ilm wa-ḡuhūr al-jah*⁶² (The disappearance of
14 knowledge and the appearance of ignorance) and Chapter 34 *Kayfa yaqbaḡu*
15 *al-‘ilm*⁶³ (How religious knowledge will be taken away). In the last chapter, a
16 transmission from ‘Umar b. ‘Abd ‘Azīz requesting Abū Bakr b. Hazm to write
17 *‘ilm* serves to illustrate the early stages of the written fixation of *‘ilm*. Similarly,
18 the verbatim use of the “Rightly-Guided” caliphs helps a learning audience to
19 have role models of *‘ilm*, in addition to the Prophet. Both represent the earliest
20 dedicated chapters to the subject. This presumably suggests that the topic had
21 reached a development that deemed it possible to include it as a separate *bāb*.
22

23 *Ṭalab al-‘ilm* has two dedicated chapters, *al-Khurūj fī ṭalab al-‘ilm* (Going out in
24 pursuit of knowledge)⁶⁴ which features an account on Moses, and its
25 symmetrical counterpart in Chapter 26,⁶⁵ *al-Riḡla fī-l-mas’alat al-nāzila wa-*
26 *ta’līm ahli-hi* (Traveling in the pursuit of *‘ilm* and teaching it to family). The last
27 chapter shows a technical but also pedagogical development in the action and
28 in the theme.
29

30 Despite the fact that the term *‘ālim* is not explicit in the titles, the textual
31 characterisation of scholars is a central plot that unfolds throughout the treatise,
32 where three chapters can be said to be unique in comparison to previous *‘ilm*
33 narratives.
34

35 3. Originality and authority in the *Kitāb al-‘ilm*.

36 *Faḡl al-‘ilm* (Superiority of knowledge)⁶⁶ is the title of the first chapter in the
37 *Kitāb al-‘ilm*. It constitutes one of the earliest instances of this collocation in the
38 title of a *muṣannaf*. The originality of this *bāb* is that it does not include any
39 report, but two *āyas* of *sūras* (Q 58: 11) and (Q 20: 114):
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42 61 al-Dārimī, *Kitāb al-Musnad al-Jāmi‘*, ed. Nabīl al-Ghamrī, pp. 123-219; ed. Ḥusayn Salīm
43 Asad al-Dārānī, vol. 1, pp. 228-506. See also, Rosenthal, *Knowledge*, p. 76.

44 62 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 53.

45 63 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 59.

46 64 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 52.

47 65 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 56.

48 66 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 45.

1 Allāh will raise those who have believed among you and those who were given knowledge, by
2 degrees. And Allāh is acquainted with what you do.

3 My Lord, increase me in knowledge.

4 The inclusion of these two *āyas* seems to be enough for al-Bukhārī to expose
5 what *‘ilm* entails. The Qur’ān does not have an attestation of this lexical
6 construction. *Faḍl* appears with *‘alīman* (knower) in Q 4: 70, and *al-‘ālamīn*
7 (worlds) in Q 2: 251. The textual evidence of *faḍl* continues throughout the
8 book, evidenced in a prophetic report in subchapter 20,⁶⁷ *Faḍl man ‘alīma wa-*
9 *‘allama* (The superiority of whoever learns and teaches):

10 The example of guidance and knowledge sent to me by Allāh is like abundant rain on the
11 ground, one that absorbed rainwater and made herbage and grass grow in abundance. Some
12 were grounds that were barren and held the water and Allāh favoured people with it; they drank,
13 made their animals drink and cultivated the land. There was another side but it was plain land
14 and could not hold water nor crop. The first exemplifies one who understands Allāh's creed and
15 benefits from what Allāh has revealed through me; he learns and then teaches it to others. The
16 other exemplifies a person who does not care for and does not accept Allāh's guidance revealed
17 through me.

18 Portrayed as rainwater, *‘ilm* is distinguished as *‘ilm khāṣṣa* and *‘ilm ‘amma*;
19 and, by extension, two kinds of people: scholars and those that need to be
20 taught, conveying the justification and legitimacy of the *‘ulamā’*. *Faḍl al-‘ilm* is
21 an opening collocation and an early manifestation of the gradual development
22 of a motif that will become a popular expression in the textual trajectory of *‘ilm*;
23 however, it is also a statement of authority by al-Bukhārī.

24 Regarding the correlation between *‘ilm* and *‘amal* and the ranking between both
25 notions, Chapter 10, *al-‘ilm qabla al-qawl wa-l-‘amal*⁶⁸ (Knowledge comes
26 before word and action) consecrates *‘ilm* as the highest notion in the ranking. It
27 does not include *aḥādīth* and it has multiple Qur’ānic quotations. This could be
28 interpreted as al-Bukhārī's strategy to further equate *‘ilm* to the Qur’ān and its
29 superiority. It opens with the direct verbatim of God (Q 47, 19). Al-Bukhārī
30 interprets that this is a *sūra* that starts with the term *‘ilm*:

31 With respect to the words of Allāh – “Know that there is no god except Allāh” –, [this] starts with
32 “knowledge”.

33 His *tafsīr*, which is open to interpretation, suggests that *‘ilm*, is not only
34 Prophetic tradition but it is the proper verbatim that leads to *tawḥīd* (Unicity) of
35 God.⁶⁹ Subsequently, al-Bukhārī declares scholars as heirs to Muḥammad,
36 alongside other verses of the Qur’ān (Q 29: 43), (Q 39: 9):⁷⁰

37 Indeed, scholars are heirs to the Prophet, they inherited knowledge. Whoever learns from them,
38 will learn in abundance.

39 Even though these interpretations, Qur’ānic excerpts and traditions are
40 somewhat thrown at the beginning of the chapter, they function as a theme and
41 suggest an archetypal vision of *‘ilm*.

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67 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 53.

68 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 49.

69 Gimaret, Daniel. “Tawḥīd” in *El*².

70 *Sunan Abī Dāwūd*, 6 vols. (Beirut: Dār al-Risālat al-‘Ālamīya, 2009), vol. 5, p. 485; *Sunan al-Tirmidhī*, 6 vols. (Beirut: Dār Gharb al-Islāmī, 1996), vol.4, p. 385.

1 Al-Bukhārī dedicates a *bāb* to the notion of *fahm* (comprehension): chapter 14,
2 *al-Fahm fi-l-‘ilm* (Comprehension of knowledge),⁷¹ which has only one report. It
3 is an account of a palm tree and an unknown individual’s hesitation to express
4 out loud before the Prophet what type of tree it is. Similarly, to the chapter *Faḍl*
5 *al-‘aql* (The Virtue of the intellect) in the *Kitāb al-adab* of Ibn Abī Shayba,⁷² al-
6 Bukhārī attempts to indicate that one must not shy away from his or her own
7 perception. The agency of a learner derives from self-confidence, but mostly
8 emerges from the instruction in *‘ilm*.
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10 3.1. Teaching *‘ilm* to an audience: The *Kitāb al-‘ilm* as a scholar’s handbook.

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12 Around fourteen chapters⁷³ which include the term *‘ilm* in their titles are
13 dedicated to the instruction in *‘ilm*. The chapters are allocated almost in a linear
14 arrangement, functioning as a thematic cluster. The analysis of the gamut of
15 these chapters exceeds the aims of this article, however several interpretations
16 shall be outlined here.
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21 The titles of the chapters are long and detailed, echoing the *Kitāb al-adab* of Ibn
22 Abī Shayba in many ways. Pragmatic, technical instructions and conduct praxis
23 span from etiquette sitting in the room, setting the right schedule for teaching,
24 allowing enough time for the teacher to respond and asking a scholar too many
25 questions, amongst many other subjects.
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28 The chapters illuminate on a hypothetical *madrasa* classroom, casting light on
29 the performance of scholars in their religious seances, very much in the fashion
30 of *adab*, such as chapter two: *Man su‘ila ‘ilman wa-huwa mushtaghil fī ḥadīth-hi*
31 *fa-atamma al-ḥadīth thumma ajāba al-sā‘il* (Whoever is asked for a report and is
32 busy talking will finish his discussion and then respond to the questioner)⁷⁴ or
33 chapter eight: *Man qa‘ada ḥaythu yantahi bi-hi al-majlis wa-man ra’ā furjatan fi-*
34 *l-halqa fa-jalasa fi-hā* (Whoever sat at the farther end of a meeting and whoever
35 found a place in a gathering and sat).⁷⁵
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39 It is a vivid impression of a daily routine, where the instruction of *‘ilm* is now a
40 professional activity. Surprisingly, the moral controversy of accumulated wealth
41 while being a scholar is not as prominent as in the aforementioned *‘ilm*
42 narratives. This suggests that al-Bukhārī’s concern, for himself as a teacher,
43 would have been to provide a technical guide to teach *‘ilm*.
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47 Scholars should be conscious that teaching demands *adab* but also an
48 appropriate scheduling, where the ethos and teaching praxis of the Prophet is
49 taken as an example; as in Chapter eleven: *Mā kāna al-nabbī yatakhawwalu-*
50 *hum bi-l-maw‘iza wa-l-‘ilm kay lā yanfirū* (The Prophet was considerate about
51 the time of sermons and knowledge so that people would not run away);⁷⁶ or
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55 71 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 51.

56 72 Ibn Abī Shayba, *Kitāb al-adab*, ed. al-Qahwaḡī, vol. 2, p. 296, report 286.

57 73 Chapters 2, 7,8, 11,12, 26, 28, 30, 36, 37, 48.

58 74 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 45.

59 75 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 48.

60 76 al-Bukhārī, *‘Ilm*, p. 50.
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Chapter 12: *Man ja'ala li-ahl al-'ilm ayyāman ma'lūmatan* (Whoever scheduled days for people of knowledge [to teach]).⁷⁷

Similarly, what drives a scholar angry must also be taken into consideration, inasmuch as those students who fail to grasp a proper understanding and attainment of the tradition. Illustrative examples of this are: Chapter 28 *al-'Aḍab fi-l-maw'iza wa-ta'līm, idhā ra'ā mā yakra-hu* (Being angry while preaching and teaching when one sees something dislikable)⁷⁸; or Chapter 30 *Man a'āda al-ḥadīth thalāthan li-yufhamu 'an-hu* (Whoever repeats a ḥadīth thrice to make others understand)⁷⁹ and chapter 36, *Man sami'a shay'an fa-rāji'a hattā ya'rifa-hu* (Whoever listened to something and asked again until he understood).⁸⁰

Chapter 37, *Li-yuballigh al-'ilm al-shāhid al-ghā'ib* (Those present must transmit 'ilm to the absentees) is another illuminating example of the recurrent disparity between titles and *matn* of the ḥadīth in the chapters. It includes a Prophetic report in the days following the conquest of Mecca, where the Prophet narrates that Allāh gave him and nobody else, the permission to fight that day, and that this important information should be transmitted to those in absence.

The report continues, featuring 'Amr b. Sa'īd (d. 70/689-90), who is sending his troops to combat the self-proclaimed caliphate of 'Abd Allāh b. al-Zubayr (r. 24/683–72/692). 'Amr b. Sa'īd refers to the aforementioned Prophetic ḥadīth to show that only Allāh made Mecca a sanctuary, and thus, the anti-Caliph has no claim.⁸¹ Expressed as a semantic variation – (*li-yuballigh*) – of *ṭalab al-'ilm farīda*, the title conveys that transmitting the tradition of the Prophet not only entails *sunna*, but provides legitimacy and authority on the level of political actions.

The last six chapters⁸² of the book discuss different situations, the most relevant being avoiding difficult topics out of fear students may not understand or may be too embarrassed to ask. The titles are indicative of the different methods of teaching 'ilm paired with *adab*, from the perspective of both the learner and the teacher. It is perhaps the last chapter, *Man ajāba al-sā'il bi-akthar mimma sa'ala-hu* (Whoever responded to the questioner with more than what was asked for) which summarises the purpose of the book of knowledge of al-Bukhārī. It conveys that 'ilm and its transmission had reached an authoritative state where 'ilm was now conceived as a method and discipline, belonging to a developing broader order of skills (pl. 'ulūm), and where 'ilm-ḥadīth was now deemed a sophisticated and authoritative method of education in Islam as a global creed.

Conclusions.

77 al-Bukhārī, 'Ilm, p. 50.

78 al-Bukhārī, 'Ilm, p. 56.

79 al-Bukhārī, 'Ilm, p. 57.

80 al-Bukhārī, 'Ilm, p. 60.

81 Karl. V. Zetterstéen, "Amr b. Sa'īd b. Al-'Āṣ b. Umayya Al-Umawī, Known as Al-Ashdak," in *EP*; Hamilton A. R. Gibb, "'Abd Allāh b. Al-Zubayr," in *EP*.

82 Chapters 48-53, pp. 68 onwards.

1 The study of *ḥadīth* and *‘ilm* is central to understanding the earliest stages of
2 Arabic writing. As an aural transmission, *ḥadīth* is an expressed narration that
3 has an effect on a listening, learning audience which triggers a creation of
4 knowledge. In this way, early sections on *‘ilm* were motivated by an educational
5 and methodological discussion of *ḥadīth* as *‘ilm*, but these body of writings with
6 time developed into a particular textual configuration with narrative elements. As
7 a literary phenomenon in *ḥadīth* literature, *‘ilm* narratives were distinguished by
8 thematic subjects and subplots casting light upon political and historical traits of
9 their times.

10 The *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of al-Bukhārī is one of the first systematic books on knowledge
11 allocated at the beginning of a *ḥadīth* corpus. It runs parallel to preceding *‘ilm*
12 paradigms. The establishment of lexical constructions, such as *faḍl al-‘ilm* or
13 *waratha al-anbiyā’* suggests a literary framework of knowledge. Nonetheless,
14 some collocations and content material reflected in the titles of the chapters are
15 innovative.

16 The emergence of early *adab* prose prompted handbooks of behavioural
17 practices, offering a broader literary potential. In comparison to Ibn Abī Shayba,
18 al-Bukhārī’s contribution reflects the importance of exegetical *adab* within the
19 context of *ḥadīth*, in the same way as the developing textual framework of the
20 *makārim al-akhlāq* (moral characters).⁸³ The natural consequence of societal
21 change could be said to have made *‘ilm* less rigid or become more literary.

22 Similarly to the contribution of al-Shāfi‘ī, al-Bukhārī was motivated by a
23 technical approach to knowledge, enhancing the concept of *ta‘līm* (education),
24 also based on language, which is the pivotal principle of *sunna*, as a channel to
25 understanding tradition. Such would be the intent of Ibn Qutayba in the *Kitāb al-*
26 *‘ilm*, who will equate language and *‘ilm* as synonyms. The concern for a
27 methodology of *‘ilm* conveys that *‘ilm* was now a discipline and its instruction an
28 ability – quoting John Hyman:⁸⁴

29 We need to think about knowledge applied, employed, in the infinitely varied circumstances that
30 arise in the course of human life. We need to think about knowledge in action, knowledge in
31 use.

32 With al-Bukhārī, it can be said that *‘ilm* became a topic in the introductory
33 section of a *muṣannaf*, drawing upon previous *‘ilm* framework. It can be argued
34 that the natural *ḍa‘īf* character of *‘ilm* narratives could have also been
35 systematised by the *Ṣaḥīḥ*, as a canonised text. Despite the problematics of
36 later attribution and amalgamation, *‘ilm* narratives of the third/ninth century
37 represent an initial perspective towards the instruction in *‘ilm* to an audience.
38 The technical transmission of Prophetic tradition became in itself a literary

39 83 James A. Bellamy, “The Makārim al-akhlāq by Ibn Abī Dunyā. A Preliminary Study” in
40 *Muslim World* 53, no. 2 (1963): pp. 106–119; Bilal Orfali and Ramzi Baalbaki, *The Book of*
41 *Noble Character, Critical Edition of Makārim al-akhlāq wa-maḥāsīn al-ādāb wabadā’i’ al-awṣāf*
42 *wa-gharā’ib al-tashbīhāt. Attributed to Abū Manṣūr al-Tha‘alibī* (d. 429/1039). (Leiden: Brill,
43 2016).

44 84 John Hyman, *Action, Knowledge, and Will*, p. 190.

1 creation, that would excel in the prospective monographs of al-Baghdādī (d.
2 463/1071), Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr (d. 463/1071) or al-Ghazzālī (d. 505/1111).

3
4 The *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of al-Bukhārī conveys the authoritative motivation but also the
5 textual agency⁸⁵ of early ‘*ulamā*’, and traditionists as a dynamic network to
6 produce sections on ‘*ilm*. This signalled the formation of a group-orientated
7 knowledge, parallel to a developing collective consciousness of identity. Al-
8 Bukhārī generated a platform for prospective, abstract conceptualisations of
9 knowledge, but also for large scale encyclopedic *adab* works, defining other
10 branches of ‘*ilm*.
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13 Knowledge is an abstract concept to define, if not impossible. However, the
14 examination of ‘*ilm* as a theme or as a literary phenomenon, construed as a
15 discourse with a particular narrative and structural elements, is a way to tackle
16 this gap and to unveil the dynamics of a global notion in premodern Arabic
17 literature.
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58 85 Edward Said, *The World, the Text, and the Critic* (Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University
59 Press, 1983), p. 4, p. 152.
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